

STATE OF EMERGENCY DECLARATION IN NIGERIAN DEMOCRATIC HISTORY AND GOOD GOVERNANCE

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Abstract

The paper dwells on state of emergency declaration in Nigerian democratic history and good governance. Its statement of problem is the politicization of the declaration of state of emergency. The methodology of qualitative and documentary led to findings that declaration of state of emergency stemming from political motivation undermines good governance as there is no legitimacy, accountability, inclusiveness, consensus, transparency, etc. The paper concludes/recommends that state of emergency declaration should strictly adhere to constitutional provisions and be depoliticized.

1.0. Introduction

State of emergency is a constitutional guarantee that empowers a government of a state to effect policies which in ordinary sense supposed not to. But for the sake of safety and protection of its citizens can declare it before, during, or after a natural disaster, civil unrest, armed conflict, medical pandemic or other security threats.¹ Since it is a constitutional provision, it is associate with popular democracies. In developing democracies like Nigeria, the state of emergency declaration first came into existence in the 1960 constitution. It stipulated the condition under which state of emergency would be declared. But since then it has been subjected to manipulation and misinterpretation leading to its abuse. The objectivity of the declaration is not uphold. It first declaration in Western Region in 1962 left many to wander at such declaration. Meanwhile, the upheavals in Tiv division which destroyed lives and property did not get the attention of the power that be to declare state of emergency in the Northern Region.

The 1979 constitution also provided for state of emergency of declaration but the four years and three months of the Second Republic was devoid of state of emergency even though there were situations which characterized security threat. With the restoration of democracy with the 1999 constitution inserting state of emergency declaration in it, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo's tenure witnessed the slamming of state of emergency on Plateau State on May 18, 2004. Similar declaration was witnessed on 19th October, 2006 in Ekiti State. Dr. Goodluck Jonathan's administration also imposed emergency rule on Plateau State in some of its local governments on 31st December, 2011. Similar declaration was made on Adamawa, Borno and Yobe on 11th May, 2013. In the same vein on 18th March, 2025 there was declaration of state of emergency in Rivers State by president Bola Ahmad Tinubu. Members of the public especially the learned ones were critical of the declaration and questioned the legality of it. Since the declaration,

several calls for such in other states have been made. Those who are in opposition to their governors like Benue and Zamfara States made such calls on the pretext of protracted herders/farmers conflict and banditry which left many lives and property destroyed in these states respectively which the governors failed to end. Meanwhile, insecurity characterized these states before their current governors ascended to power. In the thinking of opposition if there is state of emergency declaration in these states their governors will be suspended from office during such period. Therefore, the research problem of this paper is, politicization of the declaration of state of emergency. Thus the objectives of the paper are to document state of emergency declaration in Nigerian democratic history, to critique the declaration of state of emergency and its implication on good governance. The significance of this paper is that it will fill in gap in literatures on state of emergency declaration which failed to look at the implication of such on good governance and educate politicians, members of public, policy makers, administrators, etc.

The paper is segmented into introduction which is on-going, conceptual framework, state of emergency declaration in Nigerian democratic history, state of emergency declaration: a critique, implication of state of emergency declaration on good governance and a conclusion.

2.0. Conceptual Framework

State is a condition or a set of circumstances applying at any given time. While emergency is a situation which poses an immediate risk and which requires urgent attention. Therefore, state of emergency is a condition that portends danger which needs prompt action to arrest it. That action is the declaration that there exist circumstances which put people's lives, welfare and the environment in jeopardy which need extra ordinary measure to be tackled. It is any event or incident caused by human being or nature which requires immediate response to save lives and properties from danger.²Iloh and Omisore³are in consensus with the above that emergency is a sudden condition or a state of affairs calling for immediate actions. Technically, quoting Black Law Dictionary the above authors lay a legal conception of emergency as a "legal principle excepting a person from the ordinary standard of reasonable care if that person acted instinctively to meet a sudden and urgent need for aid." This legal conception is limited to an individual and our context is the whole state which encompasses people.

State of emergency regarding a state which comprises the people and the institutions of governance is a governmental declaration that suspends certain aspects of normal functions of government of the executive, legislative and the judicial powers of government.⁴When the normal functions of the three arms of government is suspended it means that the government is empowered to do whatever whether legal or otherwise necessary to achieve the safety of people and the protection of property and the environment. Emergency powers consist of two distinct nature that is, the power to declare a state of emergency and the power to make laws and execute them with respect to matters within the exclusive state competence in normal time, and to overstep with some exceptions, the limitations on power arising from constitutional guarantee of fundamental human rights. Therefore, which level of the government is vested with the power of declaration of state of emergency? And which arm is to actually exercise that power? In Nigeria, the constitution empowers the federal government to declare state of emergency in any part of the federation thereof. The executive arm of government through the president is to make such declaration as stipulated by the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. But the same constitution provides the federal legislature to checkmate the executive in making such proclamation by giving a nod of approval or disapproval to it. This nod regarding the approval by members of the legislature that a state of public emergency exist supposed to be by 2/3 majority members of the parliament.

Good governance supposed to associate with democratic regimes. This is because given the democratic tenets, it is considered to be a base on which good governance is realized. To Fagge⁵, good governance is the judicial management of authorities, power and the available resources for the total benefit of citizens and it is also identified with right policies. According to Oguniya cites by Tsegyu in Wuam et al⁶, good governance is always express as accountability, transparency, responsiveness, and efficient management of state resources. There exist good governance when the desired end of the state that is, justice, equity, protection of lives and property, enhanced participation, preservation of the rule of law and improved living standard of the people is accomplished. In fact, good governance embrace all aspects of the society like the government itself, legislature, judiciary, media, private sector, trade unions and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). United Nations⁷ also consents to the above and enumerate eight characteristics of good governance to include transparency, responsiveness, participation, rule of law, consensus oriented, equality and inclusiveness, effectiveness and efficiency, and accountability. These eight characteristics are explains thus transparency is to make governmental institutions and agencies decisions or the way they are run open and accessible to the public. These institutions and agencies are to be responsive to the yearning and aspiration of the public. That is, to strive to serve all the stakeholders within a reasonable time frame. They are to involve the participation of the public either direct or through legitimate intermediate institutions or representatives. When the public are informed and organized then participation has taken place. Furthermore, when there are fair legal frameworks impartially enforced by independent judiciary, and impartial and incorruptible police force it entails there is rule of law in operation. This is also manifest in full protection of human rights especially those of the minorities. The institutions and agencies should mediate between different interests in the society to meet a broad consensus on what is in the best interest of the whole community and how can this be achieved. When this happened, there is attainability of consensus oriented. More so, equity and inclusiveness as a characteristic of good governance is demonstrated when society well-being is considered. That's all members of the society feel that they have a stake in it and not excluded from the main stream of the society. Where good governance exist, there is that effectiveness and efficiency. The institutions and processes produce results that meet the needs of society while making the best use of resources at disposal. Accountability is witnessed when there is good governance for governmental institutions, private sector and civil society organizations are made accountable to the public and to their institutional stakeholders. The question who is accountable to whom varies depending on whether decisions or actions taken are internal or external to an organization or institution.

3.0. State of Emergency Declaration in Nigerian Democratic History

Declaration of state of emergency started when Nigeria became an independent democratic state on October 1, 1960. The genesis that led to the declaration of state of emergency in the Western Region on 29th May, 1962⁸revolved round the two personalities all leaders of Action Group (AG) party. Chief Jeremiah Obafemi Awolowo was the leader of A.G. and also opposition leader in the Federal Parliament. While Chief Samuel Ladoke Akintola was the Premier of Western Region and deputy leader of A.G. The personality clash between the duo and differences in opinion among the party members threw the party in crisis. The 1959 general election failed to elect A.G. alone into power at the centre. Also, the regional election that preceded independence saw the three major parties retaining dominance in their regions of origin. In the North, the Northern People's Congress (NPC) had 156 seats while AG obtained 9 seats leaving Northern Elements Progressive Union (NEPU) with 1 seat. In the East, the National Congress for Nigeria Citizens (NCNC) garnered 106 seats while the A.G. had 15 seats. Other parties in the region got 25 seats. The scenario shows that it was not feasible for the AG

to ouster these parties from power in their region. Therefore, the AG was left with the option of going into alliance with a particular or all the major parties. This was where fragmentation in opinions occurred which created two factions. One faction was led by Awolowo while the other led by Akintola. The Awolowo's camp was inclined to formation of alliance with NCNC to displace the NPC from power. On the other hand, Akintola's faction would want the maintenance of status quo so that each party would continue to have influence in its region. Hence, it sought cooperation with the NPC to have the West reckon with in the federal government distribution of resources.

As a party leader but in the Federal Parliament as an opposition leader, Awolowo still would want to be consulted before any policy decision is taken by Akintola regarding Western regional government. More so, he had that impression that Akintola is out to supplant him from the leadership of the party. In this vein, Akintola has to be sent away from the party as well be removed from his premiership. When the party adopted the ideology of democratic socialism to combine elements of public and private enterprise within the framework of national economy plan, it was not welcomed by the Akintola's camp. The above created a deep gap between the Akintola's faction and that of the Awolowo. The attempt to close this gap proved futile and when the party convened in Jos, Akintola was dismissed from the AG in February, 1962. Thereafter, a process was initiated in the Western Regional Assembly to remove him as premier. A majority members of the House of Assembly wrote a letter to the Governor Adesoji Aderemi that they no longer had confidence in Akintola as premier. In response, the Governor appointed D.S. Adegbenro. When the House met to rectify all the executive decisions, a fight ensued in the Assembly chamber to the extent that the police had to use teargas to disperse members. Already, the AG was not in good term with NPC because of its campaign for the creation of Middle Belt region for minorities from the north. Moreover, its demand which started in the 1950's that the north-south west boundary be adjusted to include all Yoruba under Western region displeased the NPC. On the other hand, NCNC which AG was seeking alliance with the progressive elements considered the crisis as an opportunity to break it dominance in the West. Therefore, AG has played into the hand of its enemies (NPC and NCNC) in coalition government at the centre. As such, the Federal Parliament relied on the 1960 constitution which provided in it under sections 65⁹ that a state of emergency existed when the federation was at war, or parliament by its resolution declared that the state of public emergency existed, or parliament by a 2/3 of all the members declared that democratic institutions in Nigeria were threatened by subversion to proclaim state of emergency in Western region. The declaration suspended the governor, premier, ministers, and parliament.¹⁰ Dr. M.A. Majekudumi, a federal Minister of Health was appointed sole administrator of the region.

Therefore, the AG crisis which culminated in the displayed of fracas on the floor of the Western regional House of Assembly under the guise of removal of Akintola as premier invited state of emergency declaration. Meanwhile, during the crisis Akintola refused his removal and contested it to the Supreme Court which ruled that, Governor Aderemi acted unconstitutionally in removing him without prior decision or resolution on the floor of the House of Assembly showing that the premier no longer command the support of the majority of the House. The Supreme Court ruling was contested by Adegbenro who appealed to the Judicial Committee of the Privy Council.

In May, 1963, it reversed Supreme Court ruling but the federal government refused to accept the Privy Council's verdict. Rather the Western regional constitution was amended retroactively to give constitutional backing to the Supreme Court's judgment. Hence at the end of emergency rule which lasted for period of six months Akintola was reinstated as the premier of Western region. The reversal of the Supreme Court verdict in the case between Adesoji v.

S.L. Akintola by Privy Council and the Action Group crisis of 1962 speeded up the making of 1963 republican constitution to do away with the remaining colonial vestiges like Privy Council in which the Supreme Court became the final court of the land.

The second and third state of emergency declaration in the democratic history of Nigeria was in Plateau and Ekiti States in 2004 and 2006 respectively. The Plateau State declaration was capitalized on ethno-religious conflict and triggered by the struggle to remove Joshua Dariye by his political opponents through President Olusegun Obasanjo.¹¹ Since the commencement of the fourth republic on 29th May, 1999 there was upsurge in ethno-religious conflict not only in Plateau but other states like Bauchi, Kano, Lagos, Borno, Yobe, Kaduna, Adamawa¹² where people were massacred in numbers. This upsurge in ethno-religious conflict provided a fertile ground for the declaration of state of emergency in Plateau State unlike others that were in similar experience. Previously, members of the “unknown” Muslim/Fulani militia invaded Yelwa and shot dead 46 Tarok Christians into a church and burnt down the church. This killing had receive no condemnation from the federal government or prominent personalities like Ibrahim Babangida. In what seemed to be a retaliation on 2nd May, 2004, presumably by Tarok (Yergam) militia descended on Yelwa in Shendam Local Government Area slaughtering over 200 Hausa/Fulani people.¹³ The killing of the Hausa/Fulani attracted large condemnation from important personalities thus on 18th May, 2004, president Olusegun Obasanjo slammed state of emergency on Plateau State. Justifying his action, Obasanjo capitalized on section 305 subsection 1c of the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and accused Joshua Dariye the governor of failing to act to end cycle of violence between Muslims and Christians in his state. He further accused him of some utterances, lackadaisical attitude and seeming uneven handedness...over contending issues which present him as not just part of the problem, but also an instigator and a threat to peace.¹⁴ The governor and the state legislators were suspended for six months of emergency rule. Major Gen. Chris Ali Rtd. an indigene of Plateau State was appointed the sole administrator. In the initial suspension of state elective officials, Obasanjo did not include the deputy governor but the National Assembly in their approval included him. During the period of emergency rule it was alleged that the London Metropolitan Police had arrested Dariye in September, 2004 on suspicious of money laundering. The police later reported that more than 90,000 pound cash was recovered from his home in London.¹⁵ He was freed on bail but still faced investigations in Britain and Nigeria. When the emergency rule ended in November, 2004, the minister of Justice Akinlolu Olujimi wrote the Plateau State Legislature detailing the allegations against Dariye. This was for it to find impunity with him and prepare for his impeachment.

The imposition of state of emergency on Ekiti State came against the background of the State legislature impeachment of the governor Ayo Fayose. The legislators accused the governor of embezzling state funds particularly the Ekiti State Poultry Project and had him and his deputy impeached on 15th October, 2006. The speaker of the Assembly Friday Aderemi immediately announced himself as the governor and was sworn-in on the same day. Meanwhile, Fayose who was hiding somewhere to avoid arrest by the Economic and Financial Crime Commission said he remained the governor. Mrs. Biodun Olujimi who was his deputy also lay claim as being acting governor. She resumed back to office and formed a parallel government with her security intact. But the speaker has since been installed as governor therefore there became three governors in Ekiti State at the same time. It was alleged that the declaration of the impeached deputy governor Mrs. Olujimi as acting governor was instigated by the People’s Democratic Party Chairman, Ahmadu Ali and Chief Bode George to create a resemblance of disorder in the state.¹⁶ To arrest the situation in Ekiti State, president Obasanjo proclaimed six months state of emergency on 15th October, 2006 saying the impeachment of the governor was a clear

usurpation of power. According to him, it has come to a sad, ridiculous and unacceptable situation in Ekiti where there is three governors. This is dangerous for democracy to tolerate this flagrant violation. The emergency declaration suspended the three governors and the legislators. On 18th October, 2006, Brigadier Gen. Rtd. Tunji Olurin was appointed sole administrator. But one analyst¹⁷ said the politics of Obasanjo third term bid when it was rejected triggered imposition of emergency rule in Ekiti State.

The fourth and fifth state of emergency declaration in Nigeria was by President Goodluck Jonathan in which on 31st December, 2011 imposed state of emergency on Plateau State in some of its local governments due to Boko Haram activities. The fifth one was proclaimed on May 13, 2013 in Yobe, Borno and Adamawa States. The declaration stemmed from the activities of Boko Haram which rendered the three state unsecured. It launched attacks on government establishments like the police stations and killed many since its emergence in 2009. In imposing the emergency, Jonathan said the growing insecurity in these troubled states compelled him to exercise his powers as enshrined in section 305 subsection 1 of the Nigerian constitution as the chief security officer of the country to declare a state of emergency in any troubled area. He maintained that it is a necessary step to halt the insurgency of the dreaded Boko Haram members who have turned down the offer of dialogue and amnesty extended to them by the Federal Government. He described the sect's activities as a calculated attempt to undermine the sovereignty of the country and as a declaration of war. The activities of the terrorists have prevented the government from performing its constitutional responsibilities and caused fear among Nigerians. The declaration left the governors and their deputies, and state legislatures intact. But the National Assembly approved that the three governors and the legislators should take instructions on security issues from the president or whoever he designated. The president should have power over the allocations to these states but only for compensation and rehabilitation of those affected by the order. These two measures were extraordinary ones not expressly allowed in the constitution. The emergency in these states were extended twice but denied at the third time.¹⁸ Behind the scene, it was intra People's Democratic Party (PDP) politics towards 2015 elections and more so, who becomes the president that triggered the proclamation.

The 6th state of emergency declaration was the one declared in Rivers State on 18th March, 2025 by president Bola Ahmed Tinubu. The genesis that led to the slamming of emergency rule on Rivers State was the politics of god father. Nyesom Wike, the former governor of Rivers State who later became the Minister of Federal Capital Territory, Abuja sought and found Siminalayi Fubara whom he thought he is calm and could be relied upon as his successor. But as soon as he was sworn-in feud developed in August, 2023 between him and his god father Wike. At start, Wike first blamed him for allowing his political structure to be usurped by his political opponents. The main issue that followed was the sharing formula of political appointees in which Wike nominated 14 commissioners and Fubara was given the opportunity to nominate 1 commissioner. When Fubara sent to the House of Assembly two names of his candidates for approval as commissioners Wike got to know in Abuja. Fubara's commissioners have no respect on him and it was instructed that the governor should not approve money exceeding 30 million naira without Wike's authority.¹⁹ Moreover, there was at each moment mutual suspicion of the governor to the extent that he was accused of associating with Wike's political enemies especially those who supported the PDP presidential ticket of Abubakar Atiku. Fubara was frustrated with this tight situation and would want to resign but was prevailed on to drop that. Series of meetings were held within and outside the country to reconcile the duo to no avail. Tinubu called to broker peace between the two failed. Wike's loyal commissioners resigned and Edison Ehie who was the speaker was appointed by the

Governor to become his chief of staff. The relationship between Fubara and Wike deteriorated to the extent 27 law makers loyal to the latter decamped from PDP to All Progressives Congress (APC). Therefore, the house was operating on parallel bases with Amaewhule leading 26 belligerent law makers while Victor Okon Jumbo became speaker with only three members to form a new House backed Fubara.

On October 29, 2023 dome edifice of the House of Assembly was riddled with dynamite. The next day 30th October, 2023 the complex was severely demolished on the excuse of having some structural defects. But it was alleged that the demolition was carried out because the governor perceived his impeachment by the House. In order to do away with Wike's men as local government chairmen, elections were to be held but there was court injunction restraining the PDP from fielding its candidates. Therefore, the governor directed his candidates to contest the election under the platform of Action People's Party (APP). When election was conducted on 5th October, 2024, Fubara's men who have contested under APP won all the 23 Local Government Areas and this infuriated Wike thus heightened the crisis. Meanwhile, all cases that were taken to state judiciary it was Fubara who won for instances, it was the Rivers State High Court that ruled that Fubara could present 2024 budget to the 4-man House of Assembly. It was the court that gave authorization that government could spend the budget as it was for the betterment of the Rivers' people. It was the court that ruled that the 27 lawmakers had defected and that the governor was at the liberty to transact government business with Oko-Jumbo led House. On the other hand, Wike won all the cases that were taken to federal judiciary in Abuja for instances, four cases brought against Fubara were won by Wike as the Supreme Court gave judgment in his favour. This was on February 18, 2025. The state allocation was stopped. The governor was asked to re-present the 2025 budget before Martins Amaewhule led House among other decisions. This triggered a wide range condemnation even by right standing lawyers across the country. Meanwhile, the case of the defected 27 members of PDP in the state Assembly was not brought to Supreme Court. Barely 24 hours of the Supreme Court judgment 27 lawmaker sent an ultimatum to Fubara to present the budget before it. Few days later, they issued another ultimatum that the governor should send a new list of commissioners as they sacked the 19 commissioners who were never screened by the House. Less than a week, the Amaewhule's Assembly served the governor and his deputy Mrs. Ngozi Nma Odu with letter of gross misconduct and were set for a probe. The House called on Department of State Security (DSS) to investigate alleged falsification of age of the Chief Judge of the state, Justice Simeon Amadi. Again a warrant of arrest was issued on Rivers State Independent Commission (RSIEC) Chairman Justice Adolphous Enebeli Rtd.¹⁹ The above shows that the Supreme Court judgment has given Wike more power to remove the governor. It was against this background coupled with the destruction of pipeline that compelled the president to invoke section 305 of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 as amended to declare a state of emergency in Rivers State with effect from 18th March, 2025. The declaration suspended the governor, his deputy and all elected members of Rivers State House of Assembly for initial period of six months. Vice Admiral Ibokette Ibas Rtd. was appointed administrator. The judiciary was to continue with its constitutional role. The administrator was not to make law but formulate regulations as that may be found necessary to do his job though subject to approval by the Federal Executive Council and promulgated by the president for the state. The National Assembly on 20th March, 2025 approved the declaration and was to form an ad hoc committee to oversee the administration of the state during the emergency period. And also a committee to mediate the political conflict while emergency rule remains in effect.²⁰

4.0. State of Emergency Declaration: A Critique

State of emergency declaration can be justified when such proclamation as outlines in section 305 of the 1999 constitution is adhered to without underlying interior political motive. But where a political vendetta by politicians is allowed to degenerate to capitalize on to impose state of emergency is an abuse altogether. And when the chief security officer of the nation who controls the forces out of political interest failed to release them to avert imminent security threat but turn round to blame the state chief executive is mischievous. The first imposition of state of emergency in the democratic history of Nigeria was politically motivated as such illegal. The illegality was validated by the Supreme Court which reinstated Akintola who was earlier sacked by the governor as premier in which the Privy Council later annulled. This annulment infuriated the NPC/NCNC coalition government at the centre as it felt that it plan to uproot the A.G. in Western region would not be achieved hence the retroactive amendment of Western region constitution to affirm the Supreme Court ruling and the making of republican constitution to have the Supreme Court as the highest court in the land where all cases terminated to. This could be understood that the country's judiciary is tied to the whims and caprices of the party in power. The NPC controlled central government could not impose state of emergency in 1965 Western region crisis in which lives and property were destroyed because it succeeded in destroying the power base of A.G and had entrenched unpopular party, the Nigerian National Democratic Party (NNDP) in power. This had set a precedent for achieving a political interest through the use of state of emergency. Obasanjo relied on Emergency Power Act of 1961 made under section 65(2) of the 1960 constitution to remove electoral officials in Plateau and Ekiti States. And there was an opportunity for the Supreme Court to null and void Obasanjo's action in the case of Plateau State which challenged emergency declaration and regulation made under it²¹ rather validated it. Therefore, it seemed the Supreme Court collaborated in the illegality. Moreover, ethno-religious outburst was not limited to Plateau State but was ravaging other states and Obasanjo choose it and imposed state of emergency to the extent of suspending elected state officials. The situation where the elected officials are accused and suspended during imposition of emergency rule for not arresting threat to total breakdown of law and order is unfair. The police, armed forces and other security agents are solely in control by the president. Governors are at the mercy of the president for the release of these forces to wade-off security danger especially when it emanated from political vendetta. The above is confirmed by F.R.A. Williams cites in Oniha²² that if there is actual breakdown of public order the president should be blamed more than the governor concerned for the federal government controls all the armed forces, the police and state security agencies. Moreover, s. 11(2) of the 1999 constitution grant states power to make laws for maintenance of law and order in the state. No state law has been enacted till date following the prior repeal of all state laws in respect of maintenance of public peace and order by s. 13 (2) No. 5 of 1999 constitution which was then in existence. It there means that it is only Public Order Act that is still applicable to the whole federation.²³ Therefore, it is unreasonable to blame the governors, the state legislators for any perceived failure to maintain public order and security which was used as a basis for their removal from office by Obasanjo and Tinubu. It is significant to note that state of emergency declaration in the democratic history of Nigeria is always emanate from political interest. Wike who secured Rivers State for Tinubu of APC in 2023 presidential election in return for Federal Capital Territory (FCT) ministerial slot for himself was embroiled in a political crisis with his "political son" Fubara whom he made governor. Fubara almost won the fight when Tinubu intervened on the side of his benefactor Wike and declared state of emergency in which Fubara was removed from office which gave Wike an edge over him when local government elections earlier conducted were annulled by the Supreme Court and their conduct by the appointed Administrator. Wike who handed over the PDP controlled state to APC by securing 20 local government councils for the party in an unpopular election declared

that the “coast is clear” for the termination of emergency rule in Rivers State. Members of the public interrogated the legitimacy of the conduct of the local government election by an “impostor,” the administrator. That the Supreme Court in its annulment of the election did not say flesh one should be organized by the administrator. That the presentation of budget by the administrator and spending of state funds are illegal hence the usurpation of democracy in Rivers State.

5.0. Implication of State of Emergency Declaration on Good Governance

In developing democracies like Nigeria as it is seen above, state of emergency declaration is used to settle political scores or parochial interests without due regard to good governance. The declaration which targeted at suspension of state elected officials first of all brought enjoyment of democratic dividends by the people to a standstill. The administrator put in place lacks legitimacy because his power and authority is not derived from the people. As such, he is not accountable to them for whatever decision he takes but the external force, the president who appointed him. The inputs from the people are not required in decision-making for rules and regulations are solely formulated and approved from Abuja for implementation. Therefore, the decisions made lacks consensus and transparency as the masses are not carried along. Since it is the president who appointed the administrator, he is responsible to him and not the masses and hardly include them in decision-making and no one could question him. Therefore, emergency rule is a bizarre of unrepresentative and unresponsive regime characteristic of authoritarianism which undermine the tenets of democracy with the aim of achieving the declarer’s propensity.

6.0. Conclusion

State of emergency is a governmental declaration that suspends certain aspects of normal functions of government of executive, legislative and the judicial powers of state government. And in their place, federal government is empower to do whatever whether legal or otherwise necessary to achieve the safety of the people and the protection of the environment. This power is invested in the federal government through the executive arm of government in which the president make such declaration as spell out in the constitution. While federal legislature checkmate the executive by either approving or disapproving. Democracy in which state of emergency operates supposed to be epitome of good governance which embraces accountability, transparency, responsiveness, efficient management of state resources, etc.

The 1962 state of emergency declaration was caused by A.G.’s crisis which later manifested on the floor of Western region House of Assembly to remove Akintola as premier. This resulted in fight among the members that police had to use teargas to disperse them. The declaration in Plateau State in 2004 was over ethno-religious crisis between the Hausa/Fulani Muslims and the Tarok Christians which culminated in killings thus capitalized on by the governor’s political opponents to have him remove. The Ekiti State declaration was in 2006 and the reason was the impeachment of the governor and his deputy by the state legislature in which the speaker became governor. Later the impeached governor, his deputy and the speaker were claiming the position of the governor at the same time thus appears there were three governors at the same time. The declaration in Plateau State in 2011 and Yobe, Borno and Adamawa States in 2013 was over Boko Haram activities which rendered these states unsecured. At the background it was intra party (PDP) politics towards 2015 election and who is to become president that motivated the declaration. The declaration in 2025 in Rivers State was over the politics of godfather between Wike the “father” and Fubara the “son.” The quarrel between the duos resulted into open crisis. All the imposition of state of emergency in the history of Nigeria is motivated by political interest. This is because the chief security officer of the nation who

controls all forces out of political interest through his agents would not release them to avert security threat only to blame the state chief executive when such occurred. The 1962 state of emergency declaration in Western region had set a precedent for subsequent declaration based on achieving political interest. The judgment of Supreme Courts over the cases of state of emergency declaration rather validated its illegality. The actual breakdown of public order the president should be held accountable because he controls all the forces than the governors. All state laws regarding maintenance of public peace and order has been repealed thereby leaving only Public Order Act which is within the purview of the president. State of emergency declaration implicates on good governance as there is no legitimacy, accountability, the people are not involved in decision-making, no consensus and transparency, no inclusiveness, etc. as such unrepresentative and unresponsive typical of authoritarianism.

It is the contention of this paper that state of emergency declaration should follow the constitution provisions as laid down in s. 305(3) a-g and other sub-sections of the section of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.²⁴ The proclamation as laid down supposed in any case does not necessarily affect the tenure of the governors or the right of the House of Assembly to seat. Political gladiators should play according to the rules of game of politics and eschew creating a scene of threat to peace and order. The deliberate entanglement of political actors in dispute for declaration of state of emergency jettison good governance for the masses whom they seek their mandate to govern. Declaration of state of emergency has negatively impacted on masses as a way of suppressing opposition or doing away with their political rivals. This is affirmed by Agbo²⁵ that one of the misconceptions associated with abuse of emergency power is to equate its employment by an incumbent federal government to emasculate and suppress its political opponents in its guise to prolong its stay in power against possible removal from office through the lawful activities of the opposition. And this certainly is not the preservation of state security. Therefore, state of emergency be declared in the spirit of the constitution as carried out by Jonathan which did not suspend state elected officials. To sum up in the words of Rizal and Hermawan²⁶, state of emergency should be based on the principle of proportionality as it provides standards on reasonableness by which the criteria for determining the existence of an “emergency” become clearer, the need formulated as a reason for the improvement to carry out actions that are emergency is proportionate, reasonable or appropriate so that the action in question must not exceed reasonableness. This is because a legal product is needed that detail clearly the interpretations and limitations of state of emergencies. The occurrence of disasters and natural calamity which expressly in s.305 of the constitution as one of the grounds for state of emergency declaration never receives attention than political vendetta that will end up suspending elected officials. Therefore, by way of conclusion, constitutional reforms should be effected to remove ambiguity inherent in the declaration of state of emergency for easy understanding and prevent its manipulation. Moreover, legislative oversight mechanisms such as setting up committee to ascertain objectivity or otherwise of the state of emergency declaration and where it negates the spirit of the declaration it should be vetoed. The declaration should be depoliticized that is, where crisis originated as a result of political differences to threaten law and order, state of emergency should not be declared but law enforcement agencies should be deployed to squash it without suspension of elected representatives. Those who are responsible for the crisis should be penalized with treason. This can be made efficacious by inserting it in constitution under emergency clause.

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